

Microwave-assisted synthesis, spectroscopy and antimicrobial studies of mono(cyclopentadienyl)titanium(IV) derivatives of bis(Schiff bases) derived from 1,1'-diacetylferrocene and 3-substituted phenyl-4-amino-5-mercapto-1,2,4-triazoles

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Abstract : The reactions of mono(cyclopentadienyl)titanium(IV) trichloride with a new class of Schiff bases (H_2L), derived by condensing 1,1'-diacetylferrocene with different 3-substituted phenyl-4-amino-5-mercapto-1,2,4-triazoles, have been studied both by a conventional stirring method and also using microwave technology. Binuclear products of type $[\{\eta^5-C_5H_5\}TiCl_2]_2 (L)$ have been isolated in both cases. Tentative structural conclusions are drawn for the reaction products based upon analysis, electrical conductance, magnetic moment and spectral (UV-Visible, IR, 1H NMR and ^{13}C NMR) data. FAB mass spectra of complexes were also recorded to confirm the binuclear structures. Studies were conducted to assess the growth inhibiting potential of the ligands and complexes against various fungal and bacterial strains.

Keywords : Titanium(IV), Schiff bases, preparation, characterization, bioactivity.

Introduction

1,2,4-Triazoles and their derivatives have long been recognized to possess various biological activities, such as anticonvulsant, antifungal, anticancer, anti-inflammatory and antibacterial properties¹⁻⁸. Several compounds containing 1,2,4-triazole rings are well known for drugs. Thus, the biochemistry of these molecules has been studied for many years. On the other hand, ferrocenyl derivatives have been reported to have antitumor, antifungal, insecticidal and plant growth regulatory activities^{9,10}. The biological activity of ferrocene compounds is closely related to their unique properties : lipophilicity and membrane permeability, low toxicity, planar chirality, redox activity and bulky structure¹¹⁻¹³. Keeping in view the biological applications of ferrocene as well as mercapto triazole compounds, it was thought worthwhile to combine the chemistry of both to design organometallic based biologically active compounds and further to probe their new biological properties upon chelation. The present paper includes the synthesis, characterization and bioactivity studies of titanium(IV) derivatives with Schiff bases derived from 1,1'-diacetylferrocene and 3-substituted phenyl-4-amino-5-mercapto-1,2,4-triazoles.

Experimental

Special precautions were taken to exclude moisture from apparatus and chemicals, as the starting material, i.e. mono(cyclopentadienyl)titanium(IV) trichloride, was susceptible to hydrolysis. Glass apparatus with standard interchangeable joints were used throughout the work. The apparatus was dried by leaving it in an electrically heated oven at 150–160 °C for several hours. Immediately before use, the apparatus was taken out of the oven and cooled to room temperature by keeping it in a desiccator or by protecting with guard tubes filled with fused calcium chloride. Special weighing tubes with standard joints were used. During the removal of volatile fractions and solvents under reduced pressure, traps of conventional design were used to prevent the back diffusion of solvent vapours into the pump or the passage of moisture from the pump. Special filtering funnels with G-4 sintered discs were used for filtering. Tetrahydrofuran was dried by distilling over sodium. Mono(cyclopentadienyl)titanium(IV) trichloride was prepared from $(C_5H_5)_2TiCl_2$ and $TiCl_4$ in *p*-xylene, as reported in the literature¹⁴. The ligands were prepared by the condensation of 1,1'-diacetylferrocene and 3-substituted phenyl-4-amino-5-mercapto-1,2,4-triazoles in ethanol¹⁵.

Synthesis of complexes :**(a) Preparation of complexes using microwave heating :**

In microwave assisted synthesis, the complexes were prepared by irradiating the reaction mixture of mono(cyclopentadienyl)titanium(IV) trichloride (0.06 mol) and the appropriate Schiff base (0.03 mol) in tetrahydrofuran (8 cm³) using triethylamine (0.06 mol) as hydrogen chloride acceptor for 10–15 min. The products were recovered from the microwave oven and dissolved in dry tetrahydrofuran, where the precipitate of triethylamine hydrochloride formed during the course of the reaction was removed by filtration and the filtrate was dried under reduced pressure. The resulting compounds were washed and recrystallized with tetrahydrofuran-petroleum ether (1 : 1 mixture). They were further subjected to checking of their purity by TLC using silica gel G.

(b) Preparation of the complexes using conventional stirring method :

To a solution of mono(cyclopentadienyl)titanium(IV) trichloride (0.06 mol) in dry tetrahydrofuran (50 cm³) the appropriate Schiff base (0.03 mol) was added. To this, triethylamine (0.06 mol) was added and the mixture was stirred for ca. 18–25 h at room temperature. Precipitated Et₃N.HCl was removed by filtration and the volume of the solution was reduced to ca. 15 cm³ under reduced pressure. The complexes so obtained were recrystallized from a tetrahydrofuran-petroleum ether (1 : 1) mixture.

The comparison between stirring method and microwave assisted method is presented in Table 1.

The details of the complexes reported in this paper are given below. The analytical data are for compounds prepared under microwave method. The analytical data for compounds prepared under stirring method deviate by ± 0.03 – 0.07% .

$[(\eta^5\text{-C}_5\text{H}_5)\text{TiCl}_2]_2(\text{L}_1)$: Yellow solid; yield (%) : 58 (stirring method), 75 (microwave method) (Found : C 48.68; H, 3.35; N, 11.25; S, 6.50. Calcd. for C₄₀H₃₄N₈S₂Cl₄Ti₂Fe : C, 48.80; H, 3.48; N, 11.38; S, 6.51%); mol. wt. found (calcd.) 984 (984.33); UV-Vis (nm) : 435.300; IR (cm⁻¹) : 3075m, 1370m, 760w, 480w (ferrocenyl group), 3000m, 1430m, 800w (C₅H₅ group), 1600m, 1580m (ν C=N), 610s (ν C-S), 455m (ν Ti-N), 385w (ν Ti-S); ¹H NMR (δ) : 6.55 (s, $\eta^5\text{-C}_5\text{H}_5$), 4.40–4.52, 4.72–4.85 (t,t ferrocenyl group), 7.50–8.15 (m, phenyl ring), 1.80 (s, CH₃); ¹³C NMR (δ) : 116.2 ($\eta^5\text{-C}_5\text{H}_5$), 68.8, 69.5, 83.4 (ferrocenyl group), 164.5 (-C=N-), 158.2 (-C-S), 18.2 (CH₃).

$[(\eta^5\text{-C}_5\text{H}_5)\text{TiCl}_2]_2(\text{L}_2)$: Yellowish-orange solid; yield (%) : 62 (stirring method), 78 (microwave method) (Found : C, 45.50; H, 3.0; N, 10.48, S, 5.97. Calcd. for C₄₀H₃₂N₈S₂Cl₆Ti₂Fe : C, 45.61; H, 3.06; N, 10.63; S, 6.08%); mol. wt. found (calcd.) : 1053 (1053.22); UV-Vis (nm) : 440, 290; IR (cm⁻¹) : 3070m, 1360m, 750w, 475w (ferrocenyl group), 3010m, 1425m, 810w (C₅H₅ group), 1605m, 1590m (ν C=N), 615s (ν C-S), 440m (ν Ti-N), 370w (ν Ti-S); ¹H NMR (δ) : 6.72 (s, $\eta^5\text{-C}_5\text{H}_5$), 4.45–4.58, 4.75–4.88 (t,t ferrocenyl group), 7.35–7.70 (m, phenyl ring), 1.82 (s, CH₃); ¹³C NMR (δ) : 118.5 ($\eta^5\text{-C}_5\text{H}_5$), 69.4, 70.2, 83.8 (ferrocenyl group), 168.5 (-C=N-), 159.6 (-C-S), 18.4 (CH₃).

$[(\eta^5\text{-C}_5\text{H}_5)\text{TiCl}_2]_2(\text{L}_3)$: Orange solid; yield (%) : 60 (stirring method), 76 (microwave method) (Found : C, 45.52; H, 2.95; N, 10.50; S, 6.00. Calcd. for C₄₀H₃₂N₈S₂Cl₆Ti₂Fe : C, 45.61; H, 3.06; N, 10.63; S, 6.08%); mol. wt. found (calcd.) : 1053 (1053.22); UV-Vis (nm) : 438, 295; IR (cm⁻¹) : 3078m, 1380m, 750w, 485w (ferrocenyl group), 3005m, 1435m, 800w (C₅H₅ group), 1600m, 1580m (ν C=N), 615s (ν C-S), 450m (ν Ti-N), 378w (ν Ti-S); ¹H NMR (δ) : 6.78 (s, $\eta^5\text{-C}_5\text{H}_5$), 4.48–4.55, 4.78–4.90 (t,t ferrocenyl group), 7.55, 8.10 (d,d phenyl ring), 1.84 (s, CH₃); ¹³C NMR (δ) :

Table 1. Comparison between stirring and microwave method

Compd.	Yield (%)		Solvent (cm ³)		Time	
	Stirring	Microwave	Stirring	Microwave	Stirring (h)	Microwave (min)
$[(\eta^5\text{-C}_5\text{H}_5)\text{TiCl}_2]_2(\text{L}_1)$	58	75	8	50	18	10
$[(\eta^5\text{-C}_5\text{H}_5)\text{TiCl}_2]_2(\text{L}_2)$	62	78	8	50	25	15
$[(\eta^5\text{-C}_5\text{H}_5)\text{TiCl}_2]_2(\text{L}_3)$	60	76	8	50	25	15
$[(\eta^5\text{-C}_5\text{H}_5)\text{TiCl}_2]_2(\text{L}_4)$	55	75	8	50	20	12
$[(\eta^5\text{-C}_5\text{H}_5)\text{TiCl}_2]_2(\text{L}_5)$	60	72	8	50	18	10

118.2 ($\eta^5\text{-C}_5\text{H}_5$), 69.5, 70.5, 83.9 (ferrocenyl group), 167.8 ($-\text{C}=\text{N}-$), 159.8 ($-\text{C}-\text{S}$), 18.4 (CH_3).

$\{(\eta^5\text{-C}_5\text{H}_5)\text{TiCl}_2\}_2(\text{L}_4)$: Yellow solid; yield (%) : 55 (stirring method), 75 (microwave method) (Found : C, 44.60; H, 3.00; N, 13.00; S, 5.82. Calcd. for $\text{C}_{40}\text{H}_{32}\text{N}_{10}\text{O}_4\text{S}_2\text{Cl}_4\text{Ti}_2\text{Fe}$: C, 44.72; H, 3.00; N, 13.03; S, 5.96%); mol. wt. found (calcd.) : 1074 (1074.32); UV-Vis (nm) : 435, 300; IR (cm^{-1}) : 3085m, 1382m, 748w, 485w (ferrocenyl group), 3010m, 1438m, 810w (C_5H_5 group), 1605m, 1590m ($\nu \text{C}=\text{N}$), 605s ($\nu \text{C}-\text{S}$), 452m ($\nu \text{Ti}-\text{N}$), 382w ($\nu \text{Ti}-\text{S}$); ^1H NMR (δ) : 6.65 (s, $\eta^5\text{-C}_5\text{H}_5$), 4.42–4.52, 4.74–4.88 (t,t ferrocenyl group), 8.02, 8.35 (d,d phenyl ring), 1.85 (s, CH_3); ^{13}C NMR (δ) : 117.5 ($\eta^5\text{-C}_5\text{H}_5$), 69.2, 69.8, 83.2 (ferrocenyl group), 165.2 ($-\text{C}=\text{N}-$), 159.0 ($-\text{C}-\text{S}$), 18.3 (CH_3).

$\{(\eta^5\text{-C}_5\text{H}_5)\text{TiCl}_2\}_2(\text{L}_5)$: Yellowish-brown solid; yield (%) : 60 (stirring method), 72 (microwave method) (Found : C, 48.00; H, 3.52; N, 10.62; S, 6.10. Calcd. for $\text{C}_{42}\text{H}_{38}\text{N}_8\text{O}_2\text{S}_2\text{Cl}_4\text{Ti}_2\text{Fe}$: C, 48.30; H, 3.66; N, 10.72; S, 6.13%); mol. wt. found (calcd.) : 1044 (1044.37); UV-Vis (nm) : 438, 290; IR (cm^{-1}) : 3080m, 1378m, 752w, 480w (ferrocenyl group), 3000m, 1435m, 800w (C_5H_5 group), 1610m, 1587m ($\nu \text{C}-\text{N}$), 612s ($\nu \text{C}-\text{S}$), 455m ($\nu \text{Ti}-\text{N}$), 380w ($\nu \text{Ti}-\text{S}$); ^1H NMR (δ) : 6.50 (s, $\eta^5\text{-C}_5\text{H}_5$), 4.38–4.50, 4.70–4.80 (t,t ferrocenyl group), 7.0–7.6 (m, phenyl ring), 3.85 (s, $-\text{OCH}_3$), 1.75 (s, CH_3); ^{13}C NMR (δ) : 115.2 ($\eta^5\text{-C}_5\text{H}_5$), 68.6, 69.5, 83.0 (ferrocenyl group), 162.5 ($-\text{C}=\text{N}-$), 156.8 ($-\text{C}-\text{S}$), 55.8 ($-\text{OCH}_3$), 18.1 (CH_3).

Results and discussion

1,1'-Diacetylferrocene, upon condensation with 3-(phenyl/2-chlorophenyl/4-chlorophenyl/4-nitrophenyl/2-methoxyphenyl)-4-amino-5-mercapto-1,2,4-triazoles in ethanol gives rise to bis(Schiff bases) (LH_2 , I) as shown in Scheme 1.

A systematic study of the reactions of mono-(cyclopentadienyl)titanium(IV) trichloride with Schiff bases (LH_2) (molar ratio 2 : 1) in anhydrous tetrahydrofuran in the presence of triethylamine either by microwave heating method or by stirring method may be represented by the following equation :

Complexes of type $\{(\eta^5\text{-C}_5\text{H}_5)\text{TiCl}_2\}_2(\text{L})$ are soluble in tetrahydrofuran, DMF, DMSO, PhNO_2 . The electrical conductance measurements in PhNO_2 show that the com-

Scheme 1. Synthetic route for ligands and complexes.

plexes are non-electrolytes. Magnetic susceptibility measurements show that they are diamagnetic.

Electronic spectra :

The electronic spectra of all the complexes show a single band in the region 440–425 nm, which was assigned to the charge transfer band and is in accordance with a $(n-1)d^0ns^0$ electronic configuration¹⁶. One more band is observed at *ca.* 310–290 nm, which may be due to intra-ligand transition.

Infrared spectra :

The bonding sites of bis(Schiff bases) involved in the

complexes have been determined by careful comparison of the IR spectra of the complexes with the spectra of ligands. The IR spectra of the ligands show broad bands at 2530–2640 cm^{-1} . This band could be assigned for the mercapto group¹⁷. However, in the complexes, this band disappears indicating formation of bond between titanium and sulphur through deprotonation. The IR spectra of the ligands and complexes show a band at *ca.* 610 cm^{-1} due to ν (C–S). The band in the complexes at *ca.* 370–385 cm^{-1} may be assigned to ν (Ti–S)¹⁸. The bands at *ca.* 1620–1630, 1580–1590 and 1500 cm^{-1} in the spectra of the ligands may be assigned to ν (C=N), ν (C=N) (ring) and ν (C=C) (phenyl) vibrations, respectively. Strong vibrations in the 1500–1600 cm^{-1} are usually associated with phenyl and C=N groups and it is normally not possible to identify such bands with particular C=C or C=N linkages. However, a stringent assignment of C=N group can be made by comparing the spectrum of the parent mercapto triazole containing N–NH₂ group with that of the ligands containing the ferrocenyl group in which N–NH₂ is replaced by N–N=CH group. Following this method, the strong band observed at 1620–1630 cm^{-1} is assigned to the ν (C=N) vibration. The spectra of the complexes show the shift of this band to lower frequency (*ca.* 15–20 cm^{-1}) indicating the coordination of azomethine nitrogen to metal. Bands in the 440–455 cm^{-1} region are assigned to ν (Ti–N) and support the coordination of azomethine nitrogens¹⁸. In addition, the absorption bands at *ca.* 3000 cm^{-1} (C–H) stretch, *ca.* 1430 cm^{-1} (C–C) stretch and *ca.* 800 cm^{-1} (C–H out-of-plane deformation) in all the complexes are assigned to the cyclopentadienyl group and indicate that these groups are π -bonded to the metal. Characteristic frequencies of ferrocenyl group appear at *ca.* 3080, 1380, 750 and 480 cm^{-1} .

¹H NMR spectra :

The ¹H NMR spectra of the ligands and the complexes have been recorded in DMSO-*d*₆. The δ 6.50–6.78 signals may be assigned to the cyclopentadienyl ring protons and indicate the rapid rotation of the ring about the metal-ring axis. The free Schiff bases show a signal at *ca.* 8.5 in the spectra of the ligands, due to (S–H) group which disappears in the complexes due to the deprotonation of the mercapto group. The ligands show multiplet or two doublets at δ 7.0–7.4 integrating for the aromatic group protons which shifts downfield in the complexes. This may be due to decrease in electron density after forming the complex. The complexes show a CH₃ proton signal at *ca.* δ 1.8, which is shifted downfield by 0.5–0.8

compared with the signal of the parent ligands. For ferrocenyl group, two signals appear at *ca.* δ 4.4 and 4.8.

¹³C NMR spectra :

The ¹³C NMR spectra of the ligands and their corresponding titanium complexes were recorded (Table 4) in DMSO-*d*₆. The peak due to cyclopentadienyl group appears at *ca.* δ 116 (relative to TMS). For aromatic ring and ferrocenyl group, a number of signals appear. The considerable shift in the position of carbon-1 (*ca.* δ 158.0, ligands) and carbon-3 (*ca.* δ 148.0, ligands) indicates coordination through azomethine nitrogen and mercapto group.

Thus, the above studies suggest that two thiol sulphur atoms and two azomethine nitrogen atoms of the ligands are involved in chelation. However, in the complexes reported in this paper, coordination of all the donor atoms with single titanium atom seems unlikely for steric reasons. It can be possible for one sulphur atom and one azomethine nitrogen to coordinate to one Ti^{IV} ion, while the second sulphur atom and second azomethine nitrogen of the same ligand coordinate to another titanium atom, leading to binuclear structure. The analytical data and molecular weight determination by FAB-mass spectra further supports proposed structure. Attempts are being made to develop single crystals suitable for X-ray structure, but so far no success has been achieved.

In vitro antibacterial and antifungal activity :

All bis(Schiff bases) and newly prepared mono-(cyclopentadienyl)titanium(IV) complexes were screened for their activity against four fungal organisms *Colletotrichum falcatum*, *Aspergillus niger*, *Fusarium oxysporium* and *Curvularia pallescens* and two bacteria namely *Bacillus subtilis* and *Escherichia coli* by petridishes method¹⁹. Fungicidal and bactericidal activity of each compound was evaluated at three different concentrations, i.e. 10, 100 and 1000 ppm. For each compound 1% standard solution was prepared and 1 mL of the solution was diluted with 9 mL of the solvent (DMF). Petridishes of equal diameter were sterilised at 180 °C. Stock solutions of each compound were prepared for three concentration viz. 10, 100 and 1000 ppm. Solution of 1 mL of each concentration was poured in presterilised petridishes and 9 mL of agar medium was added immediately. Each dish was rotated on the table top in order to achieve thorough mixing of medium with the compound. After this, fungus

and bacterial strain was inoculated in the dishes (diameter 5 mm). These set were then inoculated at 30 ± 2 °C. The colony diameter of the test organism was measured with mm scale after 6 days. The percentage inhibition of the growth of the test organism was calculated by following formula

$$\% \text{ Inhibition} = 100(\text{Cd} - \text{Td})/\text{Cd}$$

where Cd = colony diameter of control and Td = colony diameter of treated set.

Each set was kept in triplicate.

The minimum inhibitory concentrations (MICs) in 1000, 100 and 10 ppm were noted. To ensure that solvent had no effect on fungal and bacterial growth, a control test was performed with test medium supplemented with DMF at the same dilutions as used in the experiment.

cell permeability mechanism and their enzymatic action may be the possible reason.

The antibacterial activity results (Table 3) also show that the activity increases on chelation. The activity of the ligands and complexes is affected by the nature of the substituents; this in relation to the lipophilicity of the ligands and their membrane permeabilities, a key factor in determining the entry inside the cell. The presence of methoxy or chloro substituents at phenyl ring increases the antibacterial activity. The compounds exhibit a better effect on the *E. coli* bacteria (Gram-negative form). This is due to the fact that the Gram-positive and Gram-negative bacteria differ markedly in their cell wall composition and nature. The cell wall of Gram-positive forms is mostly peptidoglycan or murein, whereas Gram-negative bacteria possess only 20–25% peptidoglycan.

Table 2. Antifungal activity of bis(Schiff bases) and corresponding mono(cyclopentadienyl)titanium(IV) complexes

Compd.	Average percentage inhibition after 96 h											
	<i>Colletotrichum falcatum</i>			<i>Aspergillus niger</i>			<i>Fusarium oxysporum</i>			<i>Curvularia pallescens</i>		
	1000	100	10	1000	100	10	1000	100	10	1000	100	10
H ₂ L ₁	51.6	40.0	30.2	54.0	48.8	37.0	48.2	38.4	28.6	49.6	40.8	29.8
[{(η ⁵ -C ₅ H ₅)TiCl ₂] ₂ (L ₁)]	64.2	50.6	40.0	67.5	52.8	42.0	62.0	45.6	38.1	62.8	50.7	35.4
H ₂ L ₂	68.4	58.2	52.4	70.8	64.2	58.2	67.2	54.0	47.2	60.7	51.8	44.2
[{(η ⁵ -C ₅ H ₅)TiCl ₂] ₂ (L ₂)]	82.8	76.1	67.2	90.5	80.1	67.8	80.8	70.5	64.0	79.8	70.2	61.8
H ₂ L ₃	67.2	56.8	51.3	68.2	62.2	56.8	65.1	53.6	45.3	59.2	50.0	40.2
[{(η ⁵ -C ₅ H ₅)TiCl ₂] ₂ (L ₃)]	81.2	75.8	67.0	88.0	78.5	67.0	78.8	68.2	61.5	78.1	69.1	58.5
H ₂ L ₄	52.8	41.8	32.8	55.2	42.6	36.8	50.0	39.1	30.6	54.3	46.3	29.6
[{(η ⁵ -C ₅ H ₅)TiCl ₂] ₂ (L ₄)]	65.4	54.8	40.0	68.2	55.8	44.2	64.2	52.6	39.8	65.6	50.8	34.2
H ₂ L ₅	70.8	60.2	58.4	72.4	66.7	60.9	68.4	58.3	50.1	66.7	56.2	49.8
[{(η ⁵ -C ₅ H ₅)TiCl ₂] ₂ (L ₅)]	85.2	77.2	69.5	92.8	82.5	70.1	82.0	73.6	67.8	83.2	78.0	70.5

Fluconazole was used as a standard drug for antifungal and gentamycin was used as a standard drug for antibacterial activity.

The fungicidal activity (Table 2) suggested that all the Schiff bases were found to be biologically active and their mono(cyclopentadienyl)titanium(IV) complexes showed significantly enhanced activity. This may be due to the chelation and the presence of sulphur atom. For a particular species of ligands, the compounds with R = 2-Cl, 4-Cl or 2-OCH₃ showed better activity as compared with compounds with ligands containing other substituents. The variation in the effectiveness against different organisms, as suggested by Lawrence *et al.*²⁰, depends upon the permeability of the cells or ribosomes of antimicrobial agent. Actual mechanism of increased activity of complexes is not certain but factors like solubility, dipole moment and

Table 3. Antibacterial activity of bis(Schiff bases) and corresponding mono(cyclopentadienyl)titanium(IV) complexes

Compd.	Diameter of inhibition zone (mm)	
	<i>B. subtilis</i> (Gram +ve)	<i>E. coli</i> (Gram -ve)
H ₂ L ₁	3	5
[{(η ⁵ -C ₅ H ₅)TiCl ₂] ₂ (L ₁)]	6	12
H ₂ L ₂	9	10
[{(η ⁵ -C ₅ H ₅)TiCl ₂] ₂ (L ₂)]	14	20
H ₂ L ₃	8	8
[{(η ⁵ -C ₅ H ₅)TiCl ₂] ₂ (L ₃)]	12	18
H ₂ L ₄	3	3
[{(η ⁵ -C ₅ H ₅)TiCl ₂] ₂ (L ₄)]	5	10
H ₂ L ₅	7	8
[{(η ⁵ -C ₅ H ₅)TiCl ₂] ₂ (L ₅)]	10	19
Streptomycin (standard)	22	42

Conclusions :

Mono(cyclopentadienyl)titanium(IV) complexes of bis(Schiff bases), derived from 1,1'-diacetylferrocene and 3-substituted phenyl-4-amino-5-mercapto-1,2,4-triazoles, have been synthesized by both conventional stirring method and by the use of microwaves. For the microwave assisted synthesis, 10–15 min were required to complete the reactions, while in the conventional method 18–25 h were required. The yield of the products was also less in the conventional method as compared with that obtained by the microwave synthesis. The structures of the complexes were established by analyses and spectral studies. Antifungal and antibacterial activity of the ligands and the complexes were also evaluated which showed that activity increases on chelation.

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